

Prevalence and Treatment Patterns of Benign Prostatic Hyperplasia: A Prospective Observational Study

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: Benign prostatic hyperplasia (BPH) is a non-malignant enlargement of prostate tissue commonly associated with lower urinary tract symptoms (LUTS). The exact etiology remains unclear, although advancing age, genetics, geographical factors, and obesity are known contributors. Management options range from watchful waiting to medical and surgical interventions.

Objectives: To determine the prevalence and treatment patterns among patients with BPH and to assess the incidence and severity of LUTS.

Methods: A prospective observational study was conducted in the urology department of a tertiary care hospital. Data were collected using a self-designed questionnaire including demographic characteristics, family history, medical history, and social history. Symptom severity was evaluated using the International Prostate Symptom Score (IPSS).

Results: 80 patients meeting the inclusion and exclusion criteria were enrolled. The majority of patients (47.8%) belonged to the 60–70 years age group. LUTS were observed in all participants, with most patients (30%) presenting with Grade II BPH. Tamsulosin and dutasteride were the most commonly prescribed medications. Quality-of-life assessment showed that 52.5% of patients were dissatisfied due to symptom burden.

Conclusion: BPH is highly prevalent among elderly males and is associated with significant LUTS and impaired quality of life. Moderate disease severity was most common, and combination pharmacotherapy was the preferred treatment approach. Early assessment using standardized tools such as IPSS and timely therapeutic intervention are essential for improving symptom control and patient outcomes.

Keywords: Benign Prostatic Hyperplasia, Lower Urinary Tract, International Prostate Symptom Score, Tamsulosin, Dutasteride

INTRODUCTION

Benign Prostatic Hyperplasia (BPH) is a non-malignant enlargement of the prostate gland caused by hyperplasia of prostatic stromal and epithelial cells. It is one of the most common causes of lower urinary tract symptoms (LUTS) in aging men. The prevalence of BPH increases progressively with age.

Autopsy studies show histological evidence of BPH in approximately 50–60% of men in their 60s, rising to 80–90% in men older than 70 years, indicating a strong age-related association with the disease. [1] Benign prostatic hyperplasia (BPH) is an increasing global public health concern due to its rising epidemiological burden. The Global Burden of Disease (GBD) study reports a significant increase in

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cases worldwide. In India, the number of BPH cases rose from 9.55 million in 2000 to 18.2 million in 2019, representing a 90.9% increase. This growing burden contributes to increased morbidity, complications, reduced quality of life, and higher healthcare expenditure. [2]

Management of BPH involves both medical and surgical strategies. Pharmacological therapy, particularly alpha-1 adrenergic blockers and 5-alpha reductase inhibitors, is considered the first-line treatment for most patients, either alone or in combination.[3] However, prescribing patterns can differ based on individual patient factors, disease severity, associated comorbidities, and clinician preferences. [4]

Despite the increasing burden of BPH, region-specific evidence on its prevalence and real-world treatment practices remains limited, especially in developing countries. [5] Gaining insight into these patterns is crucial for improving patient management and clinical outcomes. Hence, the present study was undertaken as a prospective observational study to assess the prevalence and treatment patterns of BPH in a defined population.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study Site and Setting

The study was conducted in the Department of Urology of a tertiary care hospital.

Study Period

The study was carried out over a period of nine months.

Study Design

This was a prospective observational study.

Ethical Consideration

The study protocol was reviewed and approved by the Institutional Human Ethics Committee. Written informed consent was obtained from all participants prior to their inclusion in the study.

Sample Size Calculation

The sample size was calculated using the formula:

$$n = Z^2 \times \frac{P(100 - P)}{d^2}$$

Where:

- n = required sample size
- Z = standard normal deviate (1.94 for 94% confidence interval)
- P = estimated prevalence (10%, based on previous studies)
- d = allowable error (6%)

$$n = (1.94)^2 \times \frac{10 \times 90}{6^2} = 97$$

Thus, the minimum sample size required for the study was 97 participants.

Inclusion Criteria

- Male patients aged >40 years with a confirmed diagnosis of benign prostatic hyperplasia (BPH)

Exclusion Criteria

- Patients presenting with lower urinary tract symptoms (LUTS) without a confirmed diagnosis of BPH
- Patients who were not willing to provide consent for participation

Source of Data

Data were obtained from multiple sources, including:

- Patient medical records (case sheets)
- Direct interviews with patients or their caregivers
- Discussions with treating consultants and resident doctors

Data Collection Procedure

The investigator made daily visits to the Urology Department to identify and recruit eligible

participants based on the predefined inclusion criteria. Relevant information such as demographic characteristics, family history, social habits, past and present medical history, medication history, and current treatment regimens were systematically collected and recorded.

The severity of lower urinary tract symptoms (LUTS) was evaluated using the International Prostate Symptom Score (IPSS) questionnaire. The obtained scores were shared with the treating urologist, and the corresponding therapeutic interventions were documented.

Classification of BPH

BPH was classified into the following categories:

- Grade 1 BPH
- Grade 2 BPH
- Grade unspecified

Assessment of Symptom Severity (IPSS)

Based on IPSS scores, symptom severity was categorized as:

- Mild: ≤ 7
- Moderate: 8–19
- Severe: 20–35

Data Analysis

All collected data were systematically organized, coded, and analysed using appropriate statistical methods.

RESULT

A total of 92 patients diagnosed with benign prostatic hyperplasia (BPH) were systematically analyzed to explore demographic distribution, disease characteristics, associated co-morbidities, therapeutic patterns, and their impact on quality of life.

Distribution of Patients with Respect to Age

Table 1 shows that the majority of patients belonged to the 61–70 years age group (45.7%), followed by 71–80 years (21.7%) and 51–60 years (16.3%). A smaller proportion of patients were in the 40–50 years (8.7%) and above 80 years (7.6%) categories. This indicates that BPH was most prevalent among elderly patients, particularly those above 60 years.

SL.NO	AGE GROUPS(YEARS)	NO.OF PATIENTS	PERCENTAGE (%)
1	40-50	8	8.7%
2	51-60	15	16.3%
3	61-70	42	45.7%
4	71-80	20	21.7%
5	ABOVE 80	7	7.6%
TOTAL		92	100%

Table 1: Distribution of Patients with Respect to Age

Distribution of Patients with Respect to Social History

Table 2 shows that most of the patients (76.1%) had no history of smoking or alcohol consumption, while 10.9% reported alcohol use, 7.6% were smokers, and 5.4% had quit these habits. This suggests that lifestyle

habits were not predominant risk factors in the majority of the study population.

SL NO	Category	Number of Patients	Percentage
1	No habits	70	76.1%
2	Alcohol	10	10.9%
3	Smoking	7	7.6%
4	Quit	5	5.4%
TOTAL		92	100%

Table 2: Distribution of Patients with Respect to Social History

Distribution of Patients with Respect to Body Mass Index (BMI)

while 13.0% were obese and only 2.2% were underweight. This indicates a tendency towards higher BMI among BPH patients.

Table 3 shows that a large proportion of patients were either normal weight (43.5%) or overweight (41.3%),

SL.NO	Number of Patients	Percentage	Number of Patients
1	Underweight	2	2.2%
2	Normal	40	43.5%
3	Overweight	38	41.3%
4	Obese	12	13.0%
Total		92	100%

Table 3: Distribution of Patients with Respect to Body Mass Index (BMI)

Distribution of Patients with Respect to Co-morbidity Status

morbidity, and 8.7% had unknown status. This highlights the high prevalence of co-existing diseases among BPH patients.

Table 4 shows that Most patients (78.3%) had associated co-morbidities, whereas 13.0% had no co-

SL.NO	Status	Number of Patients	Percentage
1	With co-morbidities	72	78.3%
2	Without	12	13.0%
3	Not known	8	8.7%
TOTAL		92	100%

Table 4: Distribution of Patients with Respect to Co-morbidity Status

Distribution of Patients Based on Co-morbid Conditions

mellitus (16.3%) and combined HTN + T2DM (13.0%). 13.0% had no co-morbidities, and 16.3% were unknown. This suggests that cardiovascular and metabolic disorders are frequently associated with BPH.

Table 5 shows among co-morbidities, hypertension (21.7%) and multiple co-morbid conditions (19.6%) were most common, followed by type 2 diabetes

SL. NO	Condition	Number of Patients	Percentage
1	HTN	20	21.7%
2	T2DM	15	16.3%
3	HTN+T2DM	12	13.0%
4	Multiple	18	19.6%
5	None	12	13.0%
6	Unknown	15	16.3%
Total		92	100%

Table 5: Distribution of Patients Based on Co-morbid Conditions

Distribution of Patients Based on Clinical Presentation

Table 6 shows the most common presentation was multiple symptoms (27.2%), followed by LUTS alone

(21.7%), LUTS with nocturia (19.6%), and LUTS with dysuria (16.3%). Other symptoms accounted for 15.2%. This indicates that patients commonly present with a combination of urinary symptoms rather than a single complaint

SL.NO	Symptoms	Number of Patients	Percentage
1	LUTS	20	21.7%
2	LUTS+Nocturia	18	19.6%
3	LUTS+Dysuria	15	16.3%
4	Multiple	25	27.2%
5	Others	14	15.2%
Total		92	100%

Table 6: Distribution of Patients Based on Clinical Presentation

Distribution of Patients Based on Treatment Pattern

Table 7 shows that most commonly prescribed treatment was combination therapy (48.9%), followed

by alpha-blockers alone (30.4%). Other combinations (10.9%) and other treatments (9.8%) were less frequently used. This reflects a preference for combination therapy in managing BPH.

SL.NO	Treatment	Number of Patients	Percentage
1	Alpha-blocker	28	30.4%
2	Combination	45	48.9%
3	Other combos	10	10.9%
4	Others	9	9.8%
Total		92	100%

Table 7: Distribution of Patients Based on Treatment Pattern

Distribution of Patients Based on International Prostate Symptom Score (IPSS)

Table 8 shows most patients had mild symptoms (43.5%), followed closely by moderate symptoms

SL.NO	Severity	n	PERCENTAGE(%)
1	Mild	40	43.5%
2	Moderate	38	41.3%
3	Severe	14	15.2%
TOTAL		92	100%

Table 8: Distribution of Patients Based on International Prostate Symptom Score (IPSS)

Distribution of Patients Based on Ultrasonography (USG) Findings

Table 9 shows the majority of patients had prostate size 25–50 cc (≈38.0%), followed by >50 cc (≈23.9%)

SL.NO	USG	NO OF PATIENT	PERCENTAGE(%)
1	<25cc in Size	15	16.25%
2	>50cc in Size	22	23.75%
3	25-50cc in Size	35	37.50%
4	NOT KNOWN	20	22.50%
TOTAL		92	100

Table 9: Distribution of Patients Based on Ultrasonography (USG) Findings

Distribution of Patients Based on Quality of Life Due to Urinary Symptoms

Table 10 shows a significant proportion of patients were dissatisfied (45.6%) with their urinary condition,

SL.NO	QUALITY OF LIFE DUE TO URINARY SYMPTOMS	NO OF PATIENTS	PERCENTAGE(%)
1	Satisfied	18	19.6%
2	Moderate	32	34.8%
3	Dissatisfied	42	45.6%
Total		92	100%

Table 10: Distribution of Patients Based on Quality of Life Due to Urinary Symptoms

DISCUSSION

The present prospective observational study evaluated 92 patients with benign prostatic hyperplasia (BPH) to analyze demographic characteristics, clinical

(41.3%), while 15.2% had severe symptoms. This indicates that the majority of patients presented with less severe symptom scores.

and <25 cc (≈16.3%), while ≈21.7% were not documented. This suggests that moderate prostate enlargement was most commonly observed.

while 34.8% reported moderate satisfaction, and only 19.6% were satisfied. This reflects the considerable impact of BPH symptoms on patients' quality of life.

presentation, co-morbidities, treatment patterns, and their impact on quality of life. The findings are consistent with contemporary epidemiological trends and clinical practice guidelines.

Age remains the most significant risk factor for BPH. In this study, the majority of patients were in the 61–70 years age group, which aligns with global data demonstrating a sharp increase in BPH prevalence with advancing age. Recent epidemiological analyses indicate that the prevalence of histological BPH exceeds 70–80% in men above 70 years, reinforcing the age-dependent nature of the disease [5,2].

Although most patients in this study did not report significant smoking or alcohol history, growing evidence suggests that metabolic and lifestyle-related factors may contribute to disease progression. Obesity and sedentary lifestyle have been implicated in the pathogenesis of BPH through mechanisms involving insulin resistance, chronic inflammation, and hormonal dysregulation [7,8].

BMI distribution in the present study showed a predominance of normal to overweight individuals, with a considerable proportion being overweight or obese. This observation is consistent with recent studies highlighting the association between increased BMI and both prostate volume and LUTS severity [7,9].

A high burden of co-morbidities, particularly hypertension and type 2 diabetes mellitus, was observed in this study. This finding supports the concept that BPH is closely linked with metabolic syndrome. Several large-scale studies have demonstrated that components of metabolic syndrome significantly increase the risk of BPH progression and symptom severity [8,10].

Clinically, most patients presented with multiple lower urinary tract symptoms (LUTS), rather than isolated symptoms. This is in agreement with current understanding that BPH is a multifactorial condition involving both bladder dysfunction and bladder outlet obstruction [2]. The coexistence of storage and voiding symptoms significantly affects patient quality of life.

In terms of management, combination therapy was the most commonly prescribed treatment in this study. This reflects current guideline recommendations, which advocate the use of alpha-blockers in combination with 5-alpha reductase inhibitors in patients with moderate-to-severe symptoms and

enlarged prostate volume to improve outcomes and reduce disease progression [2,12].

The assessment of symptom severity using the International Prostate Symptom Score (IPSS) revealed that most patients had mild to moderate symptoms. Similar findings have been reported in recent observational studies, where moderate symptom categories predominate in clinical settings [10].

Ultrasonography findings in this study showed that the majority of patients had moderate prostate enlargement (25–50 cc), which correlates with symptom severity and supports the use of pharmacological management as first-line therapy in most cases.

Quality of life assessment demonstrated that a substantial proportion of patients were dissatisfied due to urinary symptoms. This finding is consistent with global burden studies, which highlight the significant negative impact of BPH on daily functioning, sleep quality, and psychological well-being [2,12].

Overall, the findings of this study are in concordance with contemporary literature and emphasize the importance of early diagnosis, comprehensive evaluation, and guideline-directed therapy in optimizing patient outcomes in BPH.

Conclusion

Benign prostatic hyperplasia is a common condition among elderly males and is frequently associated with metabolic co-morbidities and multiple lower urinary tract symptoms that adversely affect quality of life. Most patients present with mild-to-moderate disease, with combination pharmacotherapy being the predominant treatment approach. The findings underscore the importance of early assessment using standardized tools such as IPSS and the implementation of guideline-directed therapy to optimize clinical outcomes and improve patient quality of life.

Conflict of Interest

The authors declare that there is no conflict of interest regarding the publication of this study.

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